

Recording, Implementation and Testing of Deep Holographic Fourier-plane Wavefront Sensors

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we present a holographic approach to Fourier-plane wavefront sensing based on the design, recording, and experimental validation of pyramid-like Fourier filters. We design and print holograms for three, four and five side pyramids using a direct fringe-printing setup. We train a neural net reconstructor that maps holographic wavefront-sensor images into Zernike modal coefficients using experimental data. Our closed-loop experiments show stable correction in two turbulence regimes, demonstrating the feasibility of combining holographically recorded Fourier-plane filters with transformer-based reconstruction for adaptive optics applications.

Keywords: holography, Fourier-plane wavefront sensing, adaptive optics, deep learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive optics (AO) systems are essential for compensating phase distortions introduced by atmospheric turbulence and for enabling optical instruments to operate closer to the diffraction limit. At the core of any AO system lies the wavefront sensor (WFS), which must provide accurate information about the incoming and residual aberrations at high speed in order to drive the correction element in real time. Among the different WFS architectures, Fourier-plane wavefront sensors—and particularly the pyramid wavefront sensor (PyWFS)—are especially attractive because of their high sensitivity and favorable noise-propagation behavior [7, 8, 3, 2]. However, the PyWFS is intrinsically nonlinear and typically requires modulation or more advanced reconstruction strategies to operate robustly over a broader dynamic range [9, 4].

In parallel, holography provides a natural route for the physical realization of complex optical filters. Holographic fringe-printing techniques make possible the transfer of digitally computed interference patterns onto photosensitive media using spatial light modulators and imaging optics, enabling the fabrication of thin transmission holograms that reproduce a desired optical function [10]. This makes holography especially appealing for Fourier-plane wavefront sensing, since the sensing mask can first be designed numerically and then physically recorded as a compact optical element.

A related but conceptually different approach was introduced by Andersen et al., who proposed a holographic WFS based on multiplexed holographic sensing functions [1]. In contrast, the present work does not encode modal sensing directly into the hologram, but rather aims to holographically replicate Fourier-plane sensing filters.

Recent developments have further strengthened this direction. The general formalism of Fourier-based wavefront sensing allows the focal-plane filter to be treated as a free design parameter, making it possible to describe not only the classical four-face pyramid, but also broader families of Fourier-plane sensors [3]. In parallel,

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programmable implementations based on spatial light modulators have demonstrated the experimental flexibility of Fourier-based masks [6], while transformer-based neural networks have shown strong performance for nonlinear reconstruction in nonmodulated pyramid wavefront sensing, particularly in closed-loop AO operation [5, 9].

We propose holographic Fourier-plane wavefront sensing using deep learning. Several pyramid-like Fourier filters were numerically designed, converted into computer-generated holograms, and recorded onto holographic film. The resulting holograms were then implemented in an adaptive optics bench to generate experimental data for training a transformer-based reconstructor. In our setup, aberrations were produced in a controlled way by synthesizing phase screens numerically, decomposing them into Zernike coefficients, and reproducing them with a deformable mirror. Finally, the trained reconstructor was used in closed loop to assess the performance of the holographic sensor. In this way, the present work links holographic recording, generalized Fourier-plane filtering, and learned nonlinear reconstruction within a single experimental framework.

2. HOLOGRAPHIC SENSOR DESIGN AND RECORDING

The first stage of this work consists of the numerical design and holographic recording of the Fourier-plane sensing filters. For each target geometry, a pyramid-like Fourier phase mask is first generated numerically. In this way, different filters such as three (PYR3), four (PYR4), and five (PYR5) side pyramids can be obtained within the same computational framework by changing the number of faces and the corresponding pyramid angle. Once the object wave is defined, its phasor is interfered with a tilted reference plane wave in order to generate the computer-generated hologram (CGH). The recording pattern is computed as

$$I_{CGH} = |U_{ref} + U_{obj}|^2, \quad (1)$$

where U_{obj} is the phasor of the Fourier-plane filter and U_{ref} is the tilted reference wave.

The reference tip and tilt are introduced to shift the useful diffracted information away from the zero diffraction order. The numerical generation of the recording pattern is summarized in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Numerical generation of the recording pattern. (a) Phasor of the pyramid-like Fourier filter, (b) tilted reference plane wave, and (c) computer-generated hologram (CGH) obtained from the interference pattern $|U_{ref} + U_{obj}|^2$. The reference tilt shifts the useful information away from the zero diffraction order.

The calculated CGH is then transferred to the holographic film using a custom holographic fringe printer. In the configuration used here, the recording wavelength was 635 nm and the LCOS modulator had a pixel pitch of 3.74 μm . The final relay can be configured either as a 1:1 system or with a different magnification. A demagnified configuration can effectively reduce the projected pixel pitch on the holographic film, but at the expense of a smaller printable area. In addition, changing the magnification modifies the scale of the recorded pattern, and therefore the optical response of the hologram under illumination, which must be taken into account in the numerical design. The same procedure was repeated for the different pyramid-like filters, yielding three distinct holograms with a diameter of approximately 5 mm on the holographic film, corresponding to roughly 1.3×10^3 pixels across for an equivalent 1:1 projection from the LCOS plane. The final recorded filters are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Recorded holographic Fourier filters on the holographic film: (a) PYR3, (b) PYR4, and (c) PYR5. These holograms are the final recorded sensing elements obtained from the numerical Fourier-mask design and fringe-printing process. Their diameter is approximately 5 mm.

3. EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATION AND NEURAL RECONSTRUCTION

3.1 Optical bench implementation

After recording, the holographic Fourier filters were integrated into an optical bench in order to evaluate their propagated response as wavefront-sensing elements. The propagation bench was illuminated with a 635 nm red laser and used a 3 mm entrance pupil. A first $4f$ relay adapted the beam diameter to the deformable mirror (DM), while an additional relay stage was used to resize the DM pupil before a final $4f$ stage. The holographic Fourier filter was placed at the focal plane of this last relay, so that the recorded hologram acted as the Fourier-plane sensing mask of the system. In order to rapidly exchange sensing geometries, the holograms were mounted on a movable holder, allowing quick switching between PYR3, PYR4, and PYR5.

Under flat-DM conditions, the propagated intensity distributions correspond to the nominal response of each holographic sensor. These measured outputs represent the real pupil-plane response of the recorded filters in the optical bench and are shown in Fig. 3. The figure displays the propagation of the (a) PYR3, (b) PYR4, and (c) PYR5 holograms under plane-wave illumination.

Figure 3. Measured propagated responses of the recorded holographic Fourier filters under flat-DM conditions: (a) PYR3, (b) PYR4, and (c) PYR5. These images correspond to the nominal pupil-plane response of each holographic sensor in the optical bench.

3.2 Dataset acquisition from DM-driven aberrations

To generate the experimental dataset, arbitrary synthetic phase screens were first computed numerically and then decomposed into the first 69 Zernike coefficients used as the modal control basis of the deformable mirror. These coefficients were injected into the DM in order to reproduce controlled turbulence-like aberrations in the optical bench. For each injected aberration, the propagated response of the holographic sensor was recorded by the camera. Figure 4 shows representative examples of the measured propagated responses for the (a) PYR3, (b) PYR4, and (c) PYR5 holograms under aberrated conditions.

Figure 4. Measured propagated responses of the recorded holographic Fourier filters under DM-driven synthetic aberrations: (a) PYR3, (b) PYR4, and (c) PYR5. The aberrations were generated numerically, decomposed into Zernike coefficients, and reproduced with the deformable mirror.

For each captured frame, the corresponding ground-truth label was defined by the Zernike coefficient vector injected into the DM. In this way, each experimental sample consists of a measured holographic sensor image and its associated modal label. After calibration of the pupil positions, the individual subpupils were cropped and stacked channel-wise before being used for training. Each pupil crop was resized to 128×128 pixels, yielding an input tensor of size $B \times 3 \times 128 \times 128$ for PYR3 and $B \times 4 \times 128 \times 128$ for PYR4, where B denotes the batch size. Although the same procedure can be extended to other sensing geometries, in this work the neural reconstruction and closed-loop validation were restricted to the PYR3 and PYR4 architectures.

3.3 Transformer-based neural reconstruction

The training scheme used in this work is summarized in Fig. 5. Starting from an arbitrary input phase, the holographic sensor produces its corresponding propagated intensity response. The individual pupil images are then extracted, stacked, and fed into a transformer-based neural network, which outputs the estimated Zernike coefficients. In our implementation, the adopted architecture was GCViT, following the same family of models previously used for nonlinear pyramid-wavefront reconstruction. Two independent neural networks were trained, one for PYR3 and one for PYR4, since the number of pupil channels and the corresponding sensor responses differ between both architectures.

Figure 5. Training pipeline of the transformer-based reconstructor. An input phase generates the corresponding holographic sensor response, the propagated pupils are cropped and stacked, and the resulting tensor is fed into the neural network to estimate the Zernike coefficients. Separate networks were trained for PYR3 and PYR4.

The networks were trained using only the stacked pupil images as input, with z-score normalization applied to the data. The loss function was defined as the root-mean-square error (RMSE) between the ground-truth Zernike coefficients injected into the DM and the coefficients estimated by the network. In order to improve robustness to small experimental variations, additional perturbations were introduced during training, including pupil jitter and crop-size fluctuations. These augmentations make the reconstructor less sensitive to minor changes in pupil positioning and cropping, which is particularly important for stable experimental operation. The final result of this stage is a learned mapping from holographic sensor measurements to the first 69 Zernike coefficients, later used for closed-loop correction.

4. CLOSED-LOOP RESULTS

The final stage of this work consists of the closed-loop validation of the holographic sensor combined with the transformer-based reconstructor. In these experiments, only the PYR3 and PYR4 configurations were considered, since they were the two geometries selected for neural-network training and closed-loop operation. The same deformable mirror (DM) was used both to generate the controlled synthetic aberrations and to apply the corrective commands. In practice, arbitrary synthetic phase screens were computed numerically, decomposed into the first 69 Zernike coefficients, and injected into the DM. The trained neural network then estimated these 69 modal coefficients from the holographic sensor measurements, and the estimated correction was fed back to the DM through an integral controller with gain 0.3.

Two aberration regimes were tested. The first corresponds to a weaker regime, associated with an equivalent Fried parameter of approximately $r_0 = 30$ cm. The closed-loop evolution for this case is shown in Fig. 6, where the Strehl ratio (SR) is plotted as a function of iteration for PYR3 and PYR4. Before closing the loop, the aberrated state presents a Strehl ratio of approximately 0.06. Once the integral control is activated, both holographic sensors are able to close the loop and maintain a stable corrected regime, reaching Strehl-ratio values of about 0.75. The corresponding point-spread functions (PSFs) are shown in Fig. 7. Panel (a) corresponds to the initial aberrated condition, indicated as point A in Fig. 6, while panels (b) and (c) show the corrected PSFs obtained after closed-loop operation for PYR3 and PYR4, respectively, corresponding to points B and C in the same plot. The Strehl ratio displayed in the lower-left corner of each PSF corresponds to the value of the selected frame.

Figure 6. Closed-loop Strehl-ratio evolution for the weak aberration regime ($r_0 \approx 30$ cm). The two curves correspond to the PYR3 and PYR4 holographic sensors operating with the same integral controller ($g = 0.3$). Point A indicates the aberrated condition before loop closure, while points B and C correspond to representative corrected frames used in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Representative PSFs for the weak aberration regime. (a) PSF before closed-loop correction, corresponding to point A in Fig. 6; (b) corrected PSF for PYR3, corresponding to point B; and (c) corrected PSF for PYR4, corresponding to point C. The Strehl ratio of each displayed frame is indicated in the lower-left corner of the corresponding image.

A second experiment was carried out under a stronger aberration regime, corresponding to an equivalent Fried parameter of approximately $r_0 = 7.5$ cm. The corresponding Strehl-ratio evolution is shown in Fig. 8. In this case, the correction is more challenging and the Strehl ratio presents larger temporal fluctuations. Nevertheless, both the holographic sensor and the trained reconstructor remain stable throughout the sequence, and the loop converges toward a corrected regime with Strehl ratios around 0.5. Before correction, the initial aberrated state

exhibits a Strehl ratio of approximately 0.02. The corresponding PSFs are presented in Fig. 9. As before, panel (a) shows the PSF prior to loop closure, while panels (b) and (c) correspond to representative corrected frames for PYR3 and PYR4, respectively. The Strehl-ratio values shown in the lower-left corner of the PSFs correspond to the frames marked in the evolution plot.

Figure 8. Closed-loop Strehl-ratio evolution for the strong aberration regime ($r_0 \approx 7.5$ cm). The correction remains stable for both PYR3 and PYR4, although with stronger temporal variations than in the weak-aberration case. Point A indicates the initial aberrated condition, while points B and C correspond to the representative corrected frames shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. Representative PSFs for the strong aberration regime. (a) PSF before closed-loop correction, corresponding to point A in Fig. 8; (b) corrected PSF for PYR3, corresponding to point B; and (c) corrected PSF for PYR4, corresponding to point C. The Strehl ratio of each displayed frame is indicated in the lower-left corner of the corresponding image.

Overall, these results show that the holographically recorded Fourier-plane sensors, combined with transformer-based modal reconstruction, can sustain stable closed-loop correction under both weak and strong aberration regimes. Although the stronger case presents a more variable temporal behavior, the loop remains stable and achieves a clear improvement with respect to the uncorrected condition in both PYR3 and PYR4.

5. CONCLUSION

This work presented an optical-computational framework for holographic Fourier-plane wavefront sensing, including the numerical design of pyramid-like Fourier filters, their holographic recording, their implementation in an adaptive optics bench, the acquisition of experimental sensor data, the training of transformer-based reconstructors, and their validation in closed-loop operation. The results demonstrate that holographically recorded Fourier-plane filters can operate as functional wavefront-sensing elements and can be successfully combined with learned modal reconstruction for adaptive optics applications.

An important outcome of this study is that, even without a direct comparison against a conventional glass pyramid during the reconstruction stage, the proposed holographic sensor was able to estimate aberrations and sustain stable closed-loop correction under two different aberration regimes. These results indicate that holographically recorded pyramid-like filters can support effective neural reconstruction and closed-loop operation.

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